

8T – Quantum Deflections & Gravity and Mass

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Abstract:

By analyzing the primordial coupling constants equation alongside the Quark series, the author present the set of potential deflections by two scalar coefficients, \mathcal{N}^{div} and \mathcal{N}^{con} which dictate the orientation of the total deflection. There are overall two ways to analyze deflections, by the inverse ratios of the series, or by Gravity which rises from large scale formations Fermionic formations reach in Electrons. Those ways to not contradict each other. The author analyzed how Curvature is canceling the mass of the particle in Quantum scales. that is by gathering the insight of the direction of propagation.

Introduction

The main pillars of the 8T can be classified as part of two subclasses. The first subclass is curvature diverging, isomorphic to prime numbers, an idea which yielded the primordial coupling series. The series takes the form which is invariant to all coupling terms, i.e. $8 + (1)$ for the first and $8 \times (\mathcal{P}_n) + (K)$ for the higher coupling terms, in which the parameter (K) is composed of invariant three, i.e. the Lepton and the max prime in a prime sequence, (\mathcal{P}_n) , under a real range, standing for the Boson. That is $(K) = 3 + (\mathcal{P}_n)$.

$$\left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_{V\mu} + (e^-)_{\mu} \right) + N_{V\mu} = 30: 128: 850: 9254 \dots \quad (1)$$

The theory is also considering the mass sequence to be of the form $8 - (1)$ given by a decrease pattern of all masses given by the ratio aspiring zero.

$$19,600 \rightarrow 1400 \rightarrow 56$$

$$176,400 \rightarrow 1400 \rightarrow 6.3 \rightarrow 0.113 \rightarrow$$

The subject matter in hand is the following question: what would be the interaction between quantum masses and interactions?

The first case is the following – the amount of curvature diverging is equalized by the curvature converging. In that case the total interaction would be linear and no curvature will be manifested in either direction.

$$8 + (1) + 8 - (1) = 0$$

There will be no manifestation of force. The second case is the in which the curvature diverging is stronger or larger in amount than the curvature converging, in this case there will be a positive net belong to the diverging ripple the Quantum mass will be "pulled" toward this curvature ripple. Curvature diverging is synonymous with force in classical physics. One will take two scalar coefficients, \mathcal{N}^{div} and \mathcal{N}^{con} to put the idea in rigor:

$$\mathcal{N}^{div}(8 + (1)) + \mathcal{N}^{con}(8 - (1)) > 0$$

$$\mathcal{N}^{div}(8 + (1)) + \mathcal{N}^{con}(8 - (1)) = \Delta\epsilon$$

$$\mathcal{N}^{div}, \mathcal{N}^{con} \in \mathbb{R}$$

as the degree of deflection. In the second case is the mass deflection by Bosonic $\Delta\epsilon$ curvature ripple. The last case is where the curvature diverging is weaker than the curvature converging, leading to a negative net, this is where the mass will bend the Bosonic curvature, i.e. a photon as an example into it's direction, and that is in one to one correspondence with the prediction of General relativity and bending of light.

$$\mathcal{N}^{div}(8 + (1)) + \mathcal{N}^{con}(8 - (1)) < 0$$

$$\mathcal{N}^{div}(8 + (1)) + \mathcal{N}^{con}(8 - (1)) = -\Delta\epsilon$$

As previously mentioned in contrast to General Relativity it is not matter itself causing the bending but rather short-ranged Bosonic composition propagating from matter. Since matter cluster is composed by infinite amount of Quarks, it provides a sufficient ground for the rise of the Graviton, which requires emitting of primes (distinct or equivalent) at the same time, by several distinct Leptons.

$$[(2N_{gravity}) + (\bar{e}^-) + (\bar{e}^-)] + \gamma + \gamma \rightarrow (2N_{gravity}) + Even \quad (2)$$

Therefore, if we apply the same elements to Quantum scale it is possible to predict that heavy nucleons will deflect light, or that high energy set of photons will deflect the trajectory of light mass particles, such as the neutrino, assuming it carries some positive mass. The same result of General Relativity light bending should be manifested and predicted in particle scales given the 8T framework of Quantum scale curvature. Take a set of elements such as a ray of photons, and compare it with the number of estimated mass particles in a star and the result would be:

$$\mathcal{N}^{con} \gg \mathcal{N}^{div}$$

That is a noticeable net curvature deflection, which is negative, i.e. oriented to the photonic ray by the star. Assuming the ray has smaller number of elements, the formation within the star will exceed the inverse ripples. That does not mean $-\Delta\epsilon$ is a strong deflection as many elements are in the star, and it represented by higher coupling term which are immensely weaker. There are two ways to examine this relation. The first by the opposite ratios, the second is by Gravity, which rises in clusters of $(8 - (1))$ as those contain many Quark formations, thus many electrons that are vital for the Graviton, which arise in large-scale mass particle formations and can be considered as a variant composition of net elements. In other words, Gravity is the more detailed version on the subject of deflection. So taking the two scalar coefficients, \mathcal{N}^{div} and \mathcal{N}^{con} does not contradict the structure of deflections given by the 8T thesis and the actual structure of gravity. To sum in several points. First, Quantum deflections can be analyzed in two different ways. The first is by the mass series, the second and more complicated is by Gravity, which rises in Mass rich environment and serve as a minor deflection to light.

Second, in cases where light is much exceeding the mass, the mass will be "pulled" toward it, and if they are equal no curvature either way. The relation above was used to express the stability of stars. That is a stability of star is given by:

$$\mathcal{N}^{div}(8 + (1)) + \mathcal{N}^{con}(8 - (1)) = 0$$

The amount curvature diverging is equal to the curvature converging is synonymous with saying that the star is stable. The same formula was used to explain how mass carrying Bosons could travel at the speed of light. That is because of their diverging curvature, the mass operator cancels out and the Boson mass carrier is not effected by their innate mass, and thus travel in linear mode as if they are massless, in other words it will travel at the speed of light.

$$8 + (1) + 8 - (1) = 0$$

Third and last point, in quantum scale, Gravity can presented by (2) as net elements diverging, leading to the formations of the spin two particles. Since Gravity is the class, both ways, diverging and converging curvature, are valid. Gravity diverging is force, Gravity converging is mass. The short range diverging are Gravitons. Photons are net curvature diverging independent and unbound, Gravitons are short ranged diverging and composed particles. Curvature can diverge inward to a point, which provide a mass for the particle, large scale mass particles formations are rich in electrons which lead to the Graviton rise and thus for the deflections as predicted by General relativity, those large scale Fermion clusters are forming higher coupling terns, which is synonymous with the weakness of Gravity. In order to make it the argument more clean:

$$\left(8 * \prod_{\nu=1}^{\nu=R} N_{\nu\mu} + (e^-)_{\mu} \right) + N_{\nu\mu} \rightarrow \text{spin } 1 | L.\text{range curvature Diverging}$$

$$\left(8 * \prod_{\nu=1}^{\nu=R} N_{\nu\mu} + \overline{(e^-)}_{\mu} + \overline{(e^-)}_{\mu} \right) + N_{\nu\mu} + N_{\nu\mu} \rightarrow \text{spin } 2 | S.\text{range curvature Diverging}$$

$$8 + (1) \rightarrow \text{Diverging curvature} \rightarrow \text{Force}$$

$$8 - (1) \rightarrow \text{Converging curvature} \rightarrow \text{Mass}$$

The interesting thing according to the classification is that Gravity is separated from mass. It arises from where mass in large scale exist, but as far one can see, it is composed by varying set of Bosons belong to the 8 + (1) class. **In other words, Gravity cancel the mass.**

$$(2N_{gravity}) + \text{Even} \in 8 + (1)$$

$$\mathcal{N}^{con}(8 - (1)) \rightarrow M_p$$

Where M_p stand for the mass particle. That is a mass positive particle moving in curvature ripple will lose its mass. We already know that result to be true in large scale, now it applicable in Quantum scale.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8T – The Grand Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

M. Ohad BT theory